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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with great pride and enthusiasm that we present the maiden edition of the *Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities*, published by the Gamji Institute for Training and Research. This inaugural publication marks a significant milestone in our commitment to fostering academic excellence and contributing to the scholarly discourse in various fields of study.

The articles featured in this edition represent a diverse range of research topics, each offering valuable insights and advancing our understanding of critical issues. The depth and breadth of the studies reflect the dedication and scholarly rigor of the authors, and we are honored to showcase their work.

We extend our heartfelt gratitude to the authors for their invaluable contributions and to the peer reviewers for their diligent efforts in ensuring the quality and integrity of the research presented. We also express our appreciation to the editorial board and support staff whose dedication and hard work have made this publication possible.

As we embark on this scholarly journey, we invite readers to engage with the research presented in this journal, to reflect on the insights offered, and to contribute to the ongoing dialogue in their respective fields. We look forward to future editions and the continued growth of the *Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities* as a platform for academic excellence and intellectual exchange.

Sincerely,

Prof. Aminu Ahmad
Chairman, Editorial Board
Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities
Gamji Institute for Training and Research

CROWDFUNDING AS THE NEW HOPE FOR FINANCING SMALL BUSINESS ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Among the major challenges to growth and development of small business entrepreneurship in Nigeria is access to capital. Small business entrepreneurship mainly sources its funds from personal savings, borrowing from conventional and development banks and government support. However, due to stringent conditions on collateral and high interest involved, most small business entrepreneurs are discouraged from assessing loan facilities from banks. Hence, to overcome these challenges, entrepreneurs now turn to what fintechs call crowd-funding alternative for equity and debts financing for both nascent and existing entrepreneurs. It is imperative for entrepreneurs to be aware and knowledgeable about the existence of crowd-funding as alternative means of financing. Therefore, the aim of this study is to create awareness, understanding and interest among entrepreneurs in Nigeria through literature reviews by focusing on how the study will fit into the crowd-funding context. From the literature review, the study identified six crowd-funding models which include: equity, lending, reward, hybrid, royalty, and donation based. The paper concludes that, hopefully, this will solve some parts of financial needs of entrepreneurs in Nigeria and should be considered as an innovative idea for sourcing finance.

Keywords: crowd-funding, financing, small business, entrepreneurship, Nigeria.

1. INTRODUCTION

Small business entrepreneurship is one essential part of the economic sector that is related to economic growth and development, as well as the creation of several economic goals (Yacoub et al., 2022). However, one of the major challenges faced by small business entrepreneurship in developing countries, most especially Nigeria, is the access to start-ups capital. This sector of the Nigerian economy depends largely on personal savings and loans from conventional and development banks, as well as government support. But, as a result of stringent conditions on collateral and high interest rates, small business entrepreneurs are discouraged from sourcing finance from banks.

Small business entrepreneurship accounts for 90 percent of all businesses, and above 50 percent of employment generation (Lu, 2018), as well as 40 percent of global GDP (World Bank, 2021). Entrepreneurs have long debated that increasing access to innovative financing to small businesses has become imperative, hence the need to overcome the challenges bedeviling small business entrepreneurship for the promotion of economic growth and development. The emergence of innovative financing (referred to by fintechs as crowd-funding) is a source of financing businesses globally, and is receiving great attention. Entrepreneurs are now shifting from the traditional mode of financing such as commercial banks and venture capitalists to funding from crowd of consumers, lenders, and small investors (Mollick, 2014; Zhang, & Chen, 2019). Crowd-funding is a means of raising funds through the internet indicating full facts, images, as well as videos describing the profitability or otherwise of business ideas or projects (Landström et al., 2019). It is an open call through internet via social media networks to attract funds from anonymous investors and donors coming from a wide range of people (Belleflamme et al., 2013; McKenny, et al., 2019; Mollick, 2014). It is an innovative technique for 21st century fintechs created for small business entrepreneurship as well as other social entrepreneurship such as donation for political party, health care, community development, creative ideas etc., (Olalekan et al., 2020), which has become a rapidly growing phenomenon and a vital alternative source of financing for business start-ups (Bruton, et al., 2015).

The main goal of crowd-funding is to ameliorate the financial impediment faced by small business entrepreneurship (Hassanudin et al., 2020). Therefore, there is urgent need to

develop an alternative tool to tackle these financial challenges of small business entrepreneurship in developing countries such as Nigeria. The aim of this study is to create awareness among small business entrepreneurship on the role of crowd-funding as the new hope for financing small business entrepreneurship in Nigeria. This is because crowd-funding is still new in Nigeria, with the awareness still very low (Soreh, 2017). However, it can play a great role in providing solution to small business entrepreneurship with regard to accessing start-up funds. Therefore, it is imperative to create awareness and enlighten entrepreneurs on the role of crowd-funding as an alternative source of funding small business entrepreneurship.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 CONCEPT OF SMALL BUSINESS ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Small business has historically been highly difficult and contentious to define; the terms small scale business, small scale industries, and small-scale entrepreneurship are used interchangeably to refer to small and medium scale enterprises. There doesn't seem to be a clear definition of small business in Nigeria or anywhere else in the world (Carpenter, 2001; Iarossi, et al., 2009). Generally speaking, different financial institutions, industries, and nations have different definitions of small-scale businesses. This is due to the variations in currency value, capital expenditure, workforce size, sales turnover, fixed capital investment, available equipment and machinery, market share, and degree of development, which makes various writers, academics, and schools have differing opinions. Hence, if a cost price of the business could be the yardstick for measuring the size of the business, then price inflation could eventually make the definition useless. Also, it might not be practical to use a company's workforce as a benchmark for measurement, since many capital-intensive businesses can function with very few workers. However, some businesses employ a high number of laborers yet only use a little amount of capital (Osadi, 2007). In developed economies like USA, UK, Germany and Japan, a small firm could be a medium-sized or large-scale enterprise in a country like Nigeria. The definition of an SME varies over time based on the policy priorities of developing organizations or agencies. It varies based on the culture and particular circumstances of the person making the definition. In addition, the definitions in use vary depending on the goals and regulations that oversee the SME industry in a given nation.

However, Small business as defined according to Almus and Nerlinger (1999) is one that is independently owned, run, and does not hold a dominant position in its industry. According to the Committee for Economic Development in the United States of America when two or more of the following characteristics are present, then that business is referred to as small business. These are: if the capital is provided by the individual owner(s) of the business, the area of operation is local, the size of the business within the industry is small when compared with the bigger units in its field.

The Federal Ministry of Industries (2001) defined small-scale firm as one that employs between 11 and 35 people and whose total costs, including working capital but excluding land costs, fall between one million and forty million naira. A small-scale firm is defined by the Nigerian Bank for Commerce and Industry (NBCI) as one having total capital of no more than N750,000, which include working capital but excludes land expense. In 1979, the Nigerian Industrial Development Bank (NIDB) classified businesses into two categories: small and medium-sized. Small businesses had investment and working capital of not more than N750,000, while medium-sized businesses operated within the range of N750,000 to N3,000,000. Small scale businesses in Nigeria as defined by the new Industrial Policy as those with a total investment of between N100,000 and N2,000,000. According to the Central Bank of Nigeria's credit guidelines for banks, small businesses are defined as those with an annual turnover of no more than N500,000 for commercial banks and as those with a capital investment of no more than N2,000,000 (excluding the cost of land) for merchant banks, with a maximum turnover of N5,000,000 (CBN, 2006). Other definitions include the one defined by the Third National Development Plan as a manufacturing establishment with fewer than ten employees or one whose machinery and equipment investment does not exceed 600,000 naira. Furthermore, small scale businesses are those that employ no more than fifty people and have investments (i.e., capital, land building, and equipment) of up to N60,000 Pre-Structural Adjustment Programme period (Pre-SAP) value, as defined by the Small-Scale Industries Association of Nigeria (1973). The Center for Management Development (CMD) defined small industry as "a manufacturing, processing, or servicing industry involved in a factory of production type of operation, employing up to 50 full-time workers."

As seen, the definition of small and medium-sized enterprises varies from country to country relative to the overall size and structure of the domestic economy. Still, it makes sense to take into account one of the most flexible definitions that fits the findings of this investigation. The definition adopted by the National Policy on Small and Medium-sized Enterprises in Nigeria, the term shall follow a classification based on dual criteria, employment, and assets (excluding land and buildings).

Table 2.1 Classification of MSMEs in Nigeria

Size Category	Employment	Assets (N million) (excluding land and buildings)
Micro enterprises	Less than 10	Less than 5
Small enterprises	10 -49	Less than 50
Medium Enterprises	50 – 99	50 – less than 500

Source: SMEDAN (2007)

Micro enterprises are those companies whose total assets (excluding land and buildings) less than Five Million Naira with a workforce not exceeding ten. Small Enterprises are those enterprises whose total assets (excluding land and building) are above Five Million Naira but not exceeding Fifty Million Naira with a total workforce of above ten, but not exceeding forty-nine employees (Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) (2007). Medium Enterprises are those enterprises with total assets (excluding land and building) above Fifty Million Naira, but not exceeding Five Hundred Million Naira with a total workforce of between 50 and 199 employees. If there exists a conflict on classification between employment and assets criteria (for example, if an enterprise has assets worth seven million naira, but employs seven persons, the employment-based classification will take precedence and the enterprise would be regarded as micro enterprise (Mpi, 2019).

2.2 CROWD-FUNDING

Today crowd-funding has become an interesting phenomenon. It is a relatively new notion that was introduced in 2006 (Lawton, & Marom, 2010). The concept of crowd-funding emerged initially in the arts and entertainment industry, but rapidly expanded to other industries following the global financial crisis (Bruton, et al., 2015). There are many definitions of crowd-funding in the literature. Crowd-funding was defined as ‘tapping a large, dispersed audience dubbed as “the crowd”, for small pledges that can sum up to incredible amounts due to the sheer numbers of participants’ (Abushaban, 2014). Crowd-funding is described as an open call to attract funds from a large audience, termed as the crowd, that contributes or invests financial resources to support a specific project through an intermediary internet-based social or crowd-funding platform (Belleflamme et al., 2013). Therefore, a broad definition of crowd-funding is tough as it covers so many current (and likely future) uses across many disciplines. Considering the focus of the study, the researcher recommends searching other definitions for academics examining new ventures and entrepreneurial finance where crowd-funding is particularly silent. A narrower definition is preferable. In an entrepreneurial context, the following definition gives insight in order to help in the evolution of the concept: Crowd-funding refers to the efforts by entrepreneurial individuals and groups – cultural, social, and for-profit and/or nonprofit – to fund their ventures by drawing on relatively small contributions from a relatively large number of individuals using internet, without standard financial intermediaries (Mollick, 2014). This definition is a useful starting point for voluntary nonprofit organizations, in general, and social entrepreneurship development in particular.

Crowd-funding is rooted in the broader concept of crowdsourcing which draws inspiration from the concepts of micro-finance and crowdsourcing (Khan, 2019; Poetz & Schreier, 2012). In one of the few comprehensive published definitions, (Schwienbacher & Larralde, 2010) definition is mentionable. They define crowd-funding as an open call, essentially through the Internet, for the provision of financial resources either in form of donation or in exchange for some form of reward and/or voting rights in order to support initiatives for specific purposes. Although the use of the Internet to make an open call may be efficient for crowdsourcing in general, it can be problematic for crowd-funding,

especially if it involves the offering of equity to the crowd. Indeed, general solicitation for equity offering is limited to publicly listed equity. Many countries also limit how many private investors a company can have (Griffin, 2012; Schwienbacher & Larralde, 2010). Crowd-funding is characterized by its flexibility on the one hand, and the other hand, its ability to adapt to environmental changes around it to fit with the objectives and policies of each country, and with the patterns of entrepreneurial projects prevailing in each country.

2.3 TYPES OF CROWD-FUNDING

Crowd-funding has been categorised into many types. This study reviewed six different types which include: equity, debt or lending, reward, hybrid, royalty based (financial models), and donation-based crowd-funding (non-financial models).

2.3.1 EQUITY BASED CROWD-FUNDING

In this model, the financiers own part of the property rights or participate in the profits or management, as previously agreed with the owner of the project. This model can achieve high financial gains, and capital can be increased significantly as a result of attracting a large number of investors who are looking for shares in a company or a successful project outside the restrictions of stock market. Brokers do not have large amounts of money to speculate in the stock market (Sharma & Lertnuwat, 2016). Equity-based crowd-funding platforms allow crowd-funders to invest in a crowd-funding project in exchange for shares or profit of the unlisted company. This crowd-funding type is similar to venture capitalist or business angel investment processes. Equity crowd-funding type often remains rarely used on an international basis as laws and regulations in many countries generate several constraints for the entrepreneur and the investor.

2.3.2 LENDING BASED CROWD-FUNDING

This model also referred to Peer-to-Peer. The idea behind this type of Crowd-funding is to cut out the mediators and get cheaper loans or as an investor, get better interest rates (Bruton, et al., 2015). It is also referred to microfinance or peer lending. It is a form in which contributors see their fund as a loan to attract interest payments at maturity. Crowd-funding have contributed to the pool for SMEs to raise funds in the form of debt finance. Massolution (2015) argued that in 2015, GBP 25 billion was raised through

crowd-funding using the approach of debt contracts. Peer-to-peer lending is very common in countries where it is difficult to get a bank loan to start a business. There are different lending club locations for a loan model based on crowd-funding in developed countries, where investors make returns to contributors in the form of interest. Although the risk associated with it is very high in some countries like Malaysia, there is business to business financial platform (B2BFinPal).

2.3.3 REWARD BASED CROWD-FUNDING

This type of financing is common in financing a product or project which is still being developed. A form of compensation for the financier is the right to pre-order the product or get the product sent when it is finished. One advantage of this form of financing is that it is an alternative market research; if the investors are not willing to invest, they are not interested in the product or project (Cumming, et al., 2020). Reward-based crowd-funding platforms offer crowd-funders tangible or symbolic rewards, such as awarding the product or meeting the creators or offering gifts, in return for funding the project. The reward-based funding type comprises the pre-selling or pre-ordering principle in which backers act as early customers that have additional advantages compared to the regular customers like having access to the product at an earlier date, at a better price or with special benefits (Mollick, 2014). The campaigner sells his product at a very cheap price in return for a pledge. The backer supporters are those that pledge for the product. It achieves the aim of ensuring the campaigners the opportunity of returning the money raised to the contributors.

2.3.4 HYBRID BASED CROWD-FUNDING

Hybrid crowd-funding is a combination of different crowd-funding models. It offers more than one approach at a time. According to Abushaban (2014), it is a campaign for capital as a loan as well as a pledge. In the form of capital, the platform focuses on business start-ups which allow the contributors to co-invest in the project in the form of venture capital. The major characteristic of crowdfunding is that the initiators of creative ideas need to supply detailed information about their ventures to the general public through the internet as a means of convincing investors to contribute. The essence of this is to reduce information asymmetry, fraud, and risk associated with the venture to the investor. There

may be benefits for both entrepreneurs and crowd-funders by using this funding model (DeBuysere, et al., 2012). Example, if an entrepreneur uses a combination of reward and loan crowd-funding, the crowd funder's payoff is both financial and non-financial or a characteristics of a reward-based model and a donation-based model where the crowd-funders are rewarded with tangible or intangible rewards (Belleflamme et al., 2021). These rewards are often in the form of gifts based on the amount of contribution.

2.3.5 ROYALTY CROWD-FUNDING

In royalty crowd-funding, the entrepreneur receives funds from crowd-funders in exchange for a royalty fee or a certain percentage of future sales or profits from the project once it starts generating revenue (Aladejebi, 2020). In this format, individuals invest money in return for a portion of the profits. The royalty model differs from the private equity model in two ways: 1) the risk profile is lower in royalty crowd-funding (i.e., capital goals are lower, and the average contribution amount is lower), and 2) funding is used to support a single project, as opposed to private equity, which is generally used to grow an existing business. The first crowd-funding websites developed, is a European-based crowd-funding website and provides a royalty option to help music bands raise enough money to accomplish a project such as recording an album or going on tour. Backers can listen to each band's music online and contribute to those they like. There is no limit to the number of days on which funding must be completed and it can take 2-3 years for a project to be fully funded (Ward & Ramachandran, 2010). Once the band reaches their funding goal, it receives the contributed money to complete their project and the funding period ends. In return for the contributions, backers share in the proceeds earned from the project; that is, revenue from the tour or profits from the sale of the financed album.

Similarly, royalty crowd-funding has been used to fund the development of mobile applications. An individual can post their idea for a new mobile app on a crowd-funding website. In exchange for financing the development costs of the mobile application, backers are entitled to a share of the future download revenue.

2.4.6 DONATION BASED

In this model, individuals donate to the project without expecting any financial return or percentage from the project owner. This model also known as charity model is for

humanitarian purposes like natural disasters, health cases, poverty, conflicts, political parties and other charity fields (Hörisch, 2015). Donation-based crowd-funding platforms consider crowd-funders as philanthropists since they offer donations without any expected return, but simply acting to support an entrepreneur’s project. This type of crowd-funding is also obtainable in politics among political parties where they make a call to donate to the party or to a particular candidate. Example, during the 2015 election in Nigeria, the candidate of All Peoples Congress (APC) Muhammadu Buhari received donations to fund his election campaign through crowd-funding.

Table 2.2 attributes of the various crowd-funding models

No.	Model	Targeted at	Tangible reward for backers (investors)	Value for Entrepreneurs
1.	Equity based	Start-ups	Financial return, ownership stake	A possibility to get funding in return for equity
2.	Lending based	Existing businesses for one year	Financial return, debt and interest	Lower cost and easier to get than bank loan
3.	Reward based	Start-ups	Gift, pre-order-product	No need to repay money, “pre-sales” function
4.	Hybrid based	Start-ups/social services	Gift or no tangible return	No repayment
5.	Royalty based	Start-ups	Financial return, a percentage of revenue	No need to part with equity or acquire debt

6.	Donation based	Social causes, charity, political campaigns	No tangible return	Charity, No need to repay money
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Source: Author

2.5 CROWD-FUNDING AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOURCE FOR FINANCING SBE

Crowd-funding as an alternative for financing small business entrepreneurship have gained popularity in recent years. Many researchers focused on the advantages of equity crowd-funding. Ahlers et al., (2015) stated that crowd-funding provides the opportunity to minimise the risks because companies do not have to pay investors when the company has a loss. Vismara (2016), Vulkan et al. (2016), and Mochkabadi and Volkmann (2020) underlined the importance of this situation in their studies. Additionally, Lukkarinen et al. (2016), Walthoff-Borm et al. (2018), and Hornuf and Neuenkirch (2017) claimed that, with the help of equity crowd-funding, it is easier to build a strong and sustainable relationship with customers. Additionally, these types of crowd-funding have been discussed, such as reward-based crowd-funding (Frydrych et al., 2015; Kraus et al., 2016), royalty-based crowd-funding (Lu et al., 2018), and donation-based crowd-funding (Salido-Andres et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2020). However, it is difficult to continuously fund companies in this way, which is the main disadvantage.

Crowd-funding makes it possible for those with limited access to traditional financial backing sources to acquire required financial resources to pursue their projects (Gerber & Hui, 2013). It also gives people with disposable income a new way to give to others and "invest" in a project that might not happen without their financial support (Gerber & Hui, 2013). One of the significant advantages of crowd-funding is similar to that of social media, enabling initiators to make personal contacts and communicate with a large number of visitors who are interested in the future of their project and are emotionally attached to them (Kuti, & Madarász, 2014). It can be used as a promotion device to support mass customisation or used-based innovation or to understand better consumer preferences (Belleflamme et al., 2013). Crowd-funding reduces intermediation costs due to more symmetric information and the fixed low rates associated with making transfers

through its platforms (De León & Mora, 2017). Crowd-funding is a new concept that offers an alternative funding method that enables entrepreneurs to realise their original ideas (Burnaz & Demiray, 2019). According to (Jenik, et al., 2017), the advantages of using crowd-funding by SMEs include: Provision of financial resources, the investors do not need to have special knowledge about the industry, retention of management control over the company, removal of geographical barriers to investment, valuable signals about the market potential of the product/project, marketing of products and cost reduction. The benefits of donation crowd-funding include community participation and feeling of glow, voting with money, and support formalisation (Jenik, et al., 2017). The popularity of crowd-funding presents one argument for its further consideration in the academia. Another critical factor is the new advantage it offers designers as an alternative form of investment. While crowd-funding carries risks, it can also result in significant benefits for the campaigner. By exposing a product to the public, entrepreneurs can receive an extensive and varied set of feedback. Furthermore, campaigners can enjoy tremendous positive exposure to potential customers and future investors. Finally, crowd-funding favours those with innovative ideas as opposed to wealth. A campaign can be launched with minimal cost, no proof of sales, and no release of equity in three models. It is an exciting option available to entrepreneurs (Forbes & Schaefer, 2017). Crowd-funding enables entrepreneurs to verify their ideas and raise capital to develop innovative products (Jensen & Özkil, 2018).

2.6 THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVE ON CROWD-FUNDING

2.6.1 THEORY OF TRUST TRANSFER

Trust is an essential part of relationships (Art 48). Crowd-funding platforms are based on the Internet. Both the project initiators and people that will fund rarely meet; therefore, trust transference is essential. Trust can be broadly defined in ways. One broad definition is based on the expectation concerning the behaviour of an interaction partner (Garbarino & Johnson, 1999); Morgan and Hunt (1994). Another broad definition takes into cognizance the psychological state consisting acceptance of and exposure to vulnerability (Mayer et al., 1995; Rousseau et al., 2012). Benevolence, integrity, and ability are essential in trust definition (Urban et al., 2009). Crowd-funding depends on the online trust that has the components of the Internet, hardware, and software. The trust transfer theory

conceives that a consumer's trust (crowd funder's trust) may be transferred from a known target to an unknown target (Urban et al., 2009). The widely accepted definition of trust is the one given by (Mayer et al., 1995) which is the willingness of a party to be vulnerable to the action of another party based on the expectation that the other will perform a particular action necessary to the trustor, irrespective of the ability to monitor or control that other party. Trust is significant in many relationships, such as labour–management relationships, buyer-seller relationships, and strategic alliances, including crowd-funding initiators and funders.

2.5.2 THEORY OF SWIFT TRUST

Trust is based on personal knowledge of an individual's past behavior (Robert et al., 2009). Trust is built over time based on the individual's cognitive assessment of another person's behaviour (Robert et al., 2009). A high level of initial trust is called swift trust. Swift trust is developed before interaction. Swift trust is based on team member characteristics rather than on their behaviour (McKnight, et al. 1998; Meyerson, et al., 1996). An initial swift trust may be perceived as fragile (McKnight et al., 1998; Meyerson, et al., 1996; Lewicki & Bunker, 1996). Swift trust is considered a presumptive type of trust where team players who are yet to build confidence in their colleagues' ability and integrity are required to put aside uncertainty to accomplish the desired objectives (Germain, & McGuire, 2014). According to Xu, et al. (2007) and Germain, & McGuire (2014), swift trust is not interactive on a social level, but it is a precognitive trust based on action.

2.6 CROWD FUNDING PLATFORMS IN NIGERIA

For Soreh (2017), crowd-funding is a new funding innovation available to entrepreneurs and creators of innovative ideas to raise money to fund projects for a predetermined reward. The new funding innovation is yet to penetrate the fabrics of entrepreneurial finance in Nigeria but has enjoyed considerable acceptance in the USA, France, Netherlands, Britain, etc. Presently, a crowd-funding campaign for entrepreneurial activities in Nigeria is still evolving. Hence this study is conceived to scale the level of awareness and the people's attitude regarding the concept. Nigeria is said to be a host of about nine crowd-funding platforms with several listings on some of the platforms,

especially sites such as Imeela, Naturfund, Funmilowo, Donate-ng, but there is little or no evidence of successful funding for entrepreneurial activities. Some successful campaigns recorded for entrepreneurial activities in the country were listed on the platforms' websites.

2.7 REVIEW OF EMPIRICAL STUDIES ON CROWD-FUNDING

This study builds upon knowledge gained from previous studies by various scholars. Fatoki, (2014) in his study, Financing Options for New Small and Medium Enterprises in South Africa, concluded that new SMEs are vital to solving the problem of high rates of poverty and unemployment in South Africa. The failure rate of new SMEs is very high due to lack of funding by banks. The study suggested that one of the alternative means of sourcing for fund by SMEs is crowd-funding while the government should provide a good regulatory environment that will enhance the operation and management of crowd-funding. Zhao, et al. (2017) in his study, Determinants of Backers Funding Intention in Crowd-funding: Social exchange Theory and Regulatory Focus, concluded that crowd-funding had turned out to become a popular financing channel worldwide but rather the success rate of a crowd-funding project is less than 50%. The study suggested that project proponents should not only attract more visitors but to understand funding intention which leads to the success of the fundraising project. Furthermore, Golić (2014) studied the advantage of crowd-funding as alternative sources of finance SMEs. It was concluded that crowd-funding serves as alternative sources of financing new small businesses that will enhance the country's GDP. (Paschen, 2017) reported that crowd-funding has a role to play as a means of enhancing business start-up capital.

Mollick (2013) in his study, The Dynamics of Crowd-funding: An Exploratory Study, concluded that crowd-funding allows the founder of ventures to fund their effort by sourcing funds from a large number of individuals (crowd) using the internet without any standard financial intermediary. The study suggested that personal networks and underlying project quality are associated with the success of crowd-funding and that environmental and business geography is very relevant to project proposed and fundraising success. Also, Eniola and Entebang (2015), in their study on “SMEs firm performance financial innovation and challenges” concluded that SMEs have become a pivoting force of sustained, rapid, and healthy development of Nigeria's economy. The

study suggested that one of the ways of improving SMEs in Nigeria is to increase and improve financing provided through crowd-funding. Furthermore, Soreh (2017) also stated in a study on the "Awareness and Attitude towards Crowd-funding in Nigeria" that the new Funding innovation is yet to be appraised by an entrepreneur as a new form of finance. This is because crowd-funding awareness is very low at 24% as reported by the respondents while most of the respondents cannot identify any crowd-funding operating in Nigeria. The study suggested that crowd-funding is a possibility in Nigeria if people become more positive regarding the concept and embrace attitudinal change toward it as a means of funding SMEs and innovative ideas. This was also corroborated by Iddris (2019) on the role of crowd-funding in promoting micro-enterprises innovation, and thereby stated that crowd-funding awareness is key to being accepted as a source of financing reactive ideas.

Munyanyi and Mapfumo (2018) in their study, "factors influencing crowd-funding plausibility in post-hyperinflationary Zimbabwe", concluded that crowd-funding is a viable alternative means of financing entrepreneurship in Zimbabwe during the hyperinflationary period. Also, Barbi and Bigelli (2017) reported that with the advent of crowd-funding becoming popular and growing in usage as a form of financing start-up business, it might become the main source of financing new and existing businesses shortly. Furthermore, Berndt (2016) studied crowd-funding in the Africa context and concluded that there are few number of users appraising crowd-funding while information about it remains scanty. Also, Suhaili and Mohd (2017) in their study, Crowd-funding with *Waqf* reported that crowd-funding is still at the infancy stage with less emphasis for discussion by academicians. The study concluded that *waqf* as a powerful instrument for community development should embrace crowd-funding technology for fundraising. In line with this, Yu et al. (2017) recognised crowd-funding campaign as a mechanism of promoting business growth and development through alternative sources of finance. Study conducted by Okoyeuzu et al. (2019) titled Crowd-funding: An Alternative to Funding Women Entrepreneurs in Nigeria shows that barrier faced by entrepreneurs in accessing credit from traditional lenders will be solved by crowd-funding.

3 CONCLUSION

Crowd-funding as a new concept needs more attention, and the need to enlighten the public about crowd-funding opportunities, especially in poor communities where there is high unemployment and less work opportunities cannot be over-emphasised. Microfinance has become a tool of democratisation of entrepreneurship funding, while crowd-funding potentially opens entrepreneurship funding to the masses. Combining both crowd-funding and microfinance can lead to an acceleration of poverty eradication. Therefore, the review in this study shows crowd-funding is an effective funding alternative for entrepreneurs, especially SMEs.

4 RECOMMENDATIONS

As discussed earlier, the study used systematic literature review. Therefore, based on the review, the study suggested the following recommendations to improve crowd-funding as an alternative form of raising funds to small business entrepreneurship in Nigeria.

1. Awareness of crowd-funding means adequate information and better understanding of the crowd-funding concept, regulatory guide, process, benefit and risks associated with its implementation. This awareness is very important to both the fund seekers and investors. Therefore, there is the need to enlighten the public about crowd-funding opportunities available to SMEs to enable them have easy access to finance, hence, solve the problem of financial exclusion.
2. The study suggested that one of the alternative means of sourcing for a fund by SMEs is crowd-funding. Therefore, government should provide a good regulatory environment that will enhance the operation and management of crowd-funding. In addition, standards should be set for interested parties for the formation of crowd-funding platforms especially with due diligence on the promoters.
3. Government and stakeholders should focus their future efforts on developing their nations' crowd-funding ecosystem and, through this development improve SME financing possibilities through crowd-funding.
4. Business start-ups should concentrate their efforts on having a greater chance of successfully creating and running a crowd-funding campaign. To begin with, the

diaspora members of our nation's population should be targeted in crowd-funding activities and engaged as a part of the nation's crowd-funding ecosystem.

5. Since crowd-funding awareness is very low in Nigeria, and using it for funding SMEs and other creative ideas is at infant stage, there is need to create awareness for proper and better understanding of crowd-funding as alternative sources of finance. This will enhance start-up ventures and ideas to be realised which ordinarily would not have seen the light of the day.
6. Since Nigeria is ranked as one of the largest users of internet in the world. There is the need to develop trust among the users through regulation, which will help to build integrity and good relationship among the users during online transactions.
7. Funds should be mobilized towards growing creative ideas and SMEs. Developing the crowd-funding market has the potentials to eradicate poverty in Nigeria.
8. The various rules and regulations to be instituted by the Security and Exchange Commission (SEC) for crowd-funding in Nigeria should be done in protecting the general public interest and this can be achieved by disclosure requirements such as company's financial status, various risks associated with the proposed investments, names of directors and officers of the firm and the purpose of raising the funds. All these in addition to the fact that the platforms should be duly registered with the SEC.

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